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LEVELS OF HUMAN EVOLUTION, STAGES OF INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. The article focuses on the importance of intelligence in realizing the role and tasks of man in the life of society, the fact that intelligence is a fundamental concept, and its role as a philosophical category. Currently, attention is paid to the importance of artificial intelligence in development, production, science, and art, as well as the importance of individual consciousness in humans, its levels, artificial intelligence, and its management.

Keywords: intelligence, artificial intelligence, levels of consciousness, individual, evolution, criterion, citizenship, social, neighborhood, morality.

Introduction. There are many scientific hypotheses about human evolution. The latest ones are as follows: if we take into account that the estimated age of planet Earth is four and a half billion years, and human "conscious" behavior, at best, does not exceed 30,000 years according to assumptions, we understand that humanity is just getting on its feet, because its evolutionary level is very low. Based on Aristotle's idea that humans have their own morals, we see that people live according to this concept, and the consequences are deplorable. Existing moral rules are adapted to modern man, and he, like a child, treats them as toys, and to satisfy his whims, the behavior of modern man corresponds to his evolutionary age, and he does what is characteristic of this level. Since evolution is not always progressive, it can stop, retreat, and fail. There is no doubt that humanity has gone through periods when the level of human morality was much higher, but today we seem to be sliding downward at a very high speed. The reason for its decline is simple: the goal of modern education is to program people's brains so that they may not have the opportunity to do their professional and social work better. In education, the main focus is on transmitting as much information as possible, while the spiritual maturity of the individual is completely ignored or a systematic approach is lacking.

Methods. The main goal and claim of science is the idea that "Intellect is the most valuable human ability." At the same time, intelligence is viewed separately from consciousness, and we rarely think about the fact that consciousness not only determines creative intelligence but also possesses great potential depending on the high or low level of vigilance that we, unfortunately, do not use in practice.

The most valuable human virtue is the supreme consciousness, which in its

perfect manifestation became the symbol of the Logos. The word logos in a metaphysical sense was first used by Heraclitus, then this concept was developed by the Stoics, and it has retained its meaning to this day, because nature has a permanence that is denied to people. The Logos is the energy or supreme power that establishes order in the universe and governs it. Only when humanity understands what the highest consciousness is and considers it a core value will we have a cultural model that defines the highest human goal. This goal is a vertically ascending evolution. Human consciousness and it are the only meaning of existence, without which having a mind makes no sense.

We need a state capable of taking responsibility for the use of discoveries and inventions for good. Humanity suffers greatly from the irresponsibility and immorality of scientists, as science is not subject to strict ethical rules that prohibit the use of knowledge for destructive purposes.

Scientific progress is justified only if human consciousness develops in parallel with it, and this is not yet happening. Therefore, we live in a dangerous confrontation—nuclear arsenals are in the hands of those whose consciousness, from an evolutionary perspective, is, to put it mildly, in infancy. If 21st-century science could develop a device capable of studying the level of individual consciousness—that is, a person's level of awareness and their consciously accumulated experience—the situation could change. It is advisable to respond to the issues raised in the following questions and comments.

Results.

1. Establishing a scientifically irrefutable method for assessing the true significance of one person in relation to another. Higher consciousness is the main virtue, determining the value of a person in accordance with the level of consciousness. People are no longer judged by their social status, appearance, wealth, or diplomas.

2. Establishing high criteria for a person—the desire to be perfect, average, and superior.

3. To determine the lowest criteria of human imperfection based on the principles of average and low.

Based on these criteria, the most valuable people occupy the highest leadership positions in society, while the less valuable occupy ordinary positions corresponding to their mental abilities, and in extreme cases, they could be deprived of certain civil rights. At the same time, it is the duty of society to help all those who wish to develop.

We are born equal, but with the right conditions, we gradually become different due to personal perfection. We are born incomplete, and if we become so, it should not be a reason for shame or dissatisfaction, but rather an incentive for self-awareness. Society should support us in this regard, because society benefits greatly from having people who have achieved perfection.

For those who want to have full spiritual and moral rights, there should be

special schools for the development of higher consciousness so that the most important sciences can be taught and strengthened in practice. Education in such schools must be entirely voluntary, as all those who are advanced in knowledge, having seen the results obtained over time, strive to acquire this knowledge without any coercion.

The world admires and respects the geniuses of reason, but does not recognize the geniuses of consciousness; they are few and prefer to live in the unknown. Their genius is not physical, but a spiritual order. Most people will probably ask: are more conscientious people more moral?

To answer this question, we must understand that a state of transcendental consciousness precludes the possibility of causing harm to other people or engaging in immoral behavior. A person accepts this when they realize that higher consciousness is the most perfect form of spirituality that does not deny the existence of a higher mind. A high spiritual level always corresponds to a high moral and evolutionary level. The more spiritually developed a person is, the more demands they place on themselves, and the higher their level of voluntary self-management. The moral problem of humanity is the lack of individual spirituality and the drive for evolution, as such concepts are unknown to our culture. It is worth repeating that in our conventional understanding, there is no possibility of entering the secular path of spiritual development for everyone who consciously chooses it. People can't even imagine how many spiritual opportunities this path offers them.

The behavior of the average person cannot be called moral, as the overall level of human evolution is very low. Their moral level is just as low. Therefore, all attempts to impose morality based solely on recommendations about what is permissible and what is not are ineffective. If morality is not linked to consciousness, it is unlikely to be true. After all, people are only assertive in their complaints and demands and forget to be assertive when it's time to take responsibility.

Conclusion. Throughout human evolution, the development of consciousness and intelligence determines one's place in society and moral qualities. In the modern era, the evolutionary level of humanity remains very low, creating significant constraints on its cultural, moral, and spiritual development. The modern education system is aimed at transmitting more information and does not sufficiently develop a person's spiritual maturity, as a result of which they do not develop in accordance with their consciousness and mental potential.

Therefore, the higher levels of human consciousness - in particular, higher consciousness and spirituality - are of decisive importance for their place in personal and social life, moral values, and role in society. For the sustainable development of humanity, it is important to develop consciousness and intelligence, as well as to connect moral principles with consciousness. Only with such an approach can humanity fully realize its evolutionary potential and achieve high cultural and moral levels.

The pursuit of high consciousness and spirituality is the primary task of society; it is necessary to establish social norms based on the individual's striving for perfection and the level of individual consciousness, as well as to promote the full realization of every person's potential. To overcome modern threats, science and technology must be managed with moral responsibility.

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